

Investigating the Reinforcement of Social Norms in Image Search Results

Tim Gollub^a, Ann-Marie Wohlfarth^b, Pierre Achkar^{c,d}, and Benno Stein^a

^a Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, Bauhausstraße 9a, Weimar, Germany

^b Eberhard Karls University Tübingen, Burgsteige 11, Tübingen, Germany

^c Leipzig University, Augustusplatz 10, Leipzig, Germany

^d Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Martin-Luther-Ring 13, Leipzig, Germany

1. Introduction

Search engines significantly determine the dissemination of online media content and therefore, have a major influence on the reinforcement of social norms (Arias, 2019; Borg, 2022; Krytson & Eden, 2002). To this end, we analyze the search results of Web search engines and ask to which extend the top (hence mainly observed) search results for specific search queries reinforce specific social norms. In particular, we are interested in normative beauty ideals and their reinforcement in image search results. To automatically assess if the depiction of a human body in an image reinforces e.g. a contemporary Western beauty ideal, we devised and trained an effective classifier (Gollub et al., 2025), which we now apply at large scale to the search result lists of search queries to compute the ratio of images which reinforce the norm. Figure 1 illustrates the idea for the three demographic categories gender, age, and ethnicity, which we combine to different search queries. Our main finding is that the ratios differ by large margins, e.g., for the queries in Figure 1, from 6.12% for the search query "adult Indigenous female" to 83.67% for "young Asian female". We argue that from exploring the impact of different socio-demographic concepts in search queries on the ratio of norm reinforcing search results, interesting sociological hypotheses about the norm under investigation can be put forward. For example, one could argue that the Western beauty ideal that our classifier has learned promotes images of young people, as adding "young" to the search query increases the ratio. Alternatively, one could argue that search engine users who query for images of young people (or more specifically, for example, young Asian female) want to retrieve images that match the classifier's beauty ideal.

At the conference, we will present our classification workflow, together with the most striking results we obtained from composing search queries using a large pool of socio-demographic concepts,

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EMAIL: tim.gollub@uni-weimar.de (A.1); ann-marie.wohlfarth@uni-tuebingen.de (A.2); pierre.achkar@uni-leipzig.de (A.3); benno.stein@uni-weimar.de (A.4)

ORCID: 0000-0003-1737-6517 (A.1); 0009-0009-7039-7385 (A.2); 0009-0007-0791-9078 (A.3); 0000-0001-9033-2217 (A.4)

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search operators like in-domain searches, as well as translations across various languages. We hope that in reaction to our findings, an interesting discussion about their social implications will emerge.

Ethnic Group	Young		Adult		Middle Age	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
African-American	28.00%	32.00%	26.00%	22.45%	8.16%	12.00%
Asian	48.98%	83.67%	57.14%	48.00%	26.53%	28.00%
Caucasian	55.10%	56.00%	40.82%	42.00%	18.00%	28.57%
Indigenous	52.00%	12.77%	18.00%	6.12%	16.00%	6.12%
Latino	68.00%	42.00%	55.10%	52.00%	24.00%	14.00%
Middle Eastern	76.00%	48.98%	50.00%	26.00%	34.00%	10.20%

Figure 1 Percentage of images reinforcing a contemporary Western beauty ideal in the Google image search results obtained from a European IP address for search queries that are composed of an Ethnic Group, Gender, and Age Group.

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3. References

Arias, E. (2019). How does media influence social norms? Experimental evidence on the role of common knowledge. *Political Science Research and Methods*, 7(3), 561–578. <https://doi.org/10.1017/psrm.2018.1>

Borg, K. (2022). Media and social norms: Exploring the relationship between media and plastic avoidance social norms. *Environmental Communication*, 16(3), 371–387. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17524032.2021.2010783>

Gollub, T., Achkar, P., Potthast, M., & Stein, B. (2025, April). Call for research on the impact of information retrieval on social norms. In C. Hauff, C. Macdonald, D. Jannach, G. Kazai, F. M. Nardini, F. Pinelli, F. Silvestri, & N. Tonello (Eds.), *Advances in information retrieval: 47th European Conference on IR Research (ECIR 2025)* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science). Springer.

Kryston, K., & Eden, A. (2022). I like what you like: Social norms and media enjoyment. *Mass Communication and Society*, 25(5), 603–625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15205436.2021.1934703>